
Lacking pluralism? A critical review of the use of cultural dimensions in negotiation research

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Abstract

Cross-Cultural-Negotiations are pivotal in global business. Research frequently approaches this topic using cultural dimensions as underpinning conceptual constructs. This paper provides a systematic review of the use of cultural dimensions in negotiation research of more than 30 years. Empirical Cross-Cultural-Negotiation literature has been systematically searched for findings obtained by the use of Hofstede or The Globe Study dimensional constructs and categorized them into four negotiation stages. Findings show that negotiation research lacks pluralism in the use of cultural dimensions: The majority of publications use Hofstede's Individuality dimension as the main reference, whereas the remaining dimensions of Hofstede, and especially those of The Globe Study, enjoyed little attention so far - A trend that continues to exist until 2017, including. This review also shows that the use of Hofstede's Individuality dimension delivers contradictory findings in crucial research areas: Competitive vs. Cooperative Negotiation Strategy, Integrative Information Exchange, Problem Solving Approaches, and its reciprocation. Further, an analysis of research sub-categories reveals an unbalanced distribution, focussing mainly on negotiation strategies and is widely ignoring other areas of research. Implications of the findings and the use of alternative dimensional constructs of culture for future research are discussed.

Keywords Cross-Cultural-Negotiations • Hofstede • The Globe Study • Cultural Dimensions • Individuality Dimension • Competitive Negotiation Strategy • Cooperative Negotiation Strategy

JEL Classification F51 • M14 • F23

1 Introduction

Conducting Cross-Cultural-Negotiations is fundamental for companies that are involved in international business endeavors (Gulbro and Herbig 1994). Its importance cannot be overestimated since it “is one of the most important global business skills a manager can possess” (Adler and Gunderson 2008). On the one hand, intensified globalization and internationalization produced an increased demand to understand this phenomenon (Hendon 2007; Weiss 1994). On the other hand, however, there are substantial cultural differences in negotiation approaches around the globe (e.g., Brett et al. 2017; Aslani et al. 2016; Saorín-Iborra and Cubillo 2016; Vieregge and Quick 2011). Culture seems to influence and complicate the negotiation process as it affects negotiation behaviors (e.g., Kopelmann et al. 2016), communication styles (e.g., Baber and Ojala 2015), interests (e.g., Tinsely 2001), priorities (e.g., Gelfand and Christakopoulous 1999), concession patterns (Hendon 2007), and strategies used (e.g., Drake 1995). Existing literature suggests that reaching an agreement in intercultural negotiations is more difficult than in intracultural settings (e.g., Lügger 2014; Liu et al. 2012; Gelfand and Dyer 2000; Adair et al. 2001; Brett and Okumura 1998; Lituchy 1997; Adler and Graham 1989). Some authors even claim that culture is the main reason for failed international negotiations (e.g., Weiss and Stripp 1998; Gulbro and Herbig 1994). Due to this higher level of complications that cross-cultural negotiators face, successful negotiation patterns that originate from national cultural frames cannot simply be applied and transferred into an international setting. Overcoming this challenge presupposes a kaleidoscope of different business-related disciplines that come to application in unfamiliar cultural environments. Therefore it is essential to understand not only the single differences of Cross-Cultural-Negotiations but also the bigger picture of these differences. Graham et al. (1994) mentioned early the importance of providing an overview of Hofstede’s impact on Cross-Cultural-Negotiation research that allows collecting and summarizing these differences. Metcalf and Bird (2004) claim that a systematic overview that organizes and provides a categorization of research findings at a larger scale is lacking, and beyond this Gunia and Gelfand (2016) see the necessity to expand its scope beyond Hofstede, incorporating The Globe Study. Although there is already literature that provides an overview of several selected publications of Cross-Cultural-Negotiation research, for example, Gunia and Gelfand (2016) or Kirkman et al. (2006), they both comprise a relatively limited scope of studies. This paper aims to collect literature from research, investigates its conceptual origin that links to Hofstede’s or The Globe Study’s dimensions, and groups its findings along the four negotiation stages of Adair and Brett (2005). Especially involving The Globe Study allows research to refer to a comprehensive starting point to further investigate the relationship between negotiation and culture.

1.1 Research questions, approach, and contributions

1.1.1 Hofstede's Individuality dimension: A one-sided perspective onto Cross-Cultural-Negotiations

Concerning the state of the art of Cross-Cultural-Negotiation research, several pivotal questions need to be addressed: Is research narrowing its scope to mostly one framework as a conceptual construct, preferring possibly a single cultural dimension? Some authors believe that Hofstede's Individuality (IND) dimension is being used most in Cross-Cultural-Negotiation research (e.g., Inman et al. 2014; Kirkman et al. 2006; Bazerman et al. 2000; Leung 1997). Although possibly correct at first glance, there is no evidence of this claim so far. Further, considering the dimensional distribution within Hofstede's framework and The Globe Study, are there other cultural dimensions of both studies which were not considered yet that could provide a valuable contribution to research by providing insights from different conceptual perspectives? This paper enables a comprehensive approach to both questions by reviewing more than 470 publications in the research field, providing a holistic view of the literature and an analysis of its dimensional conceptual constructs linking to Hofstede and The Globe Study. It will be shown that Cross-Cultural-Negotiation research lacks pluralism in the use of cultural dimensions - Hofstede's IND dimension contributes to 72,57% of all findings within this review – a development that does not only exist in the past but until 2017, including, as a temporal analysis in this paper shows. Hence, this phenomenon is highly relevant and an up to date topic.

1.1.2 Dimensional voids in the research landscape and resulting research gaps

Another important question to be targeted in this review is whether there are dimensional constructs that only found rudimentary application, resulting in research gaps? Following the review of the research findings, the analysis of its links to cultural dimensions revealed the frequency of the findings. It will be shown that there are several cultural dimensions of both – Hofstede and The Globe Study – that have not been considered by a larger share (i.e., showing less than three findings in this review) or not been considered at all by research (i.e., showing no finding): Within this review, two findings of Hofstede's Masculinity (MAS) were identified, whereas its UAV dimension didn't find any consideration. Concerning research and its dimensional link to The Globe Study, the analysis will show that for the following dimensions, less than three findings were found: In-Group-Collectivism (G-G-COLL) dimension, Power Distance (G-PDI), Assertiveness (G-AS), Humane Orientation (G-HO), and Uncertainty Avoidance (G-UAV) dimension. And, further, there are several dimensions of The Globe Study that have not found consideration in the investigated literature at all: Institutional Collectivism (G-I-COLL), Gender Egalitarianism (G-GE), Performance Orientation (G-PO), and Future Orientation (G-FO). Due to this one-sided perspective from the IND point of view, on the one hand, it is shown that there is a conceptual impasse that distorts

the perspective onto the research field and potentially limits its development. On the other hand, this opens up several opportunities for future research that allows exploring the research field from a different angle by changing the perspective to other dimensional constructs, enabling a more diverse perception. In the discussion section, these gaps are addressed, and future avenues of research with potential links to alternative cultural dimensions are pointed out.

1.1.3 Contradictory findings delivered by Hofstede's Individuality dimension

Another question is emerging due to the nature of this review: Does the literature reveal contradictory findings that also result in future avenues for research? Following the categorization of the findings, an analysis revealed several contradictory findings from the use of Hofstede's – mainly IND dimension: First, high IND and low IND scores are associated with both competitive and cooperative negotiation strategies. Second, the use of information exchange shows a similar situation, displaying an ambiguous state of research. Further, the preference of cultures towards problem-solving approaches and their reciprocation also delivers ambiguous findings using Hofstede's IND dimension. Finally, the use of power persuasion strategies shows contradictory results in research by the use of Hofstede's PDI dimension. As a result, this situation paths the way to several avenues for future research. It will be shown that the use of additional cultural dimensions may shed new light on these ambiguous findings. All five areas displayed show the potential for application of additional conceptual constructs of cultural dimensions, but especially the field of information exchange, reciprocation of problem-solving approaches, and the use of power persuasion strategies as Table 7 displays. Further, the identified future avenues of research are linked to potential alternative cultural dimensions delivered by Hofstede's and The Globe Study's framework that allows broadening the scope of research.

1.1.4 Disproportionate focus on one research fields' sub-category: Negotiation strategies

Finally, there remains the question of whether research is underpinned by a broad distribution of different thematic sub-categories? And whether the findings are equally distributed among these sub-categories? Therefore the findings were analyzed and grouped into thematic subcategories. As a result, this analysis will show that several sub-categories of the research field can be distinguished, displaying areas with different gradations of engagement. It will be revealed that the topic of negotiation strategies is by far the most widely investigated sub-category, whereas others lack this degree of engagement. For example, first offers in negotiations only found attention sporadically in the cross-cultural-context, although the topic is considered as one of the most important for the outcome of negotiations (see, e.g., Galinsky and Mussweiler 2001). This finding, in combination with the

dimensional analysis, further shows that the topic of negotiation strategies is also dominated by Hofstede's IND dimension and hence is also viewed through a one-dimensional lens. This focus on negotiation strategies and IND produces an intertwined situation: A large number of findings in a confined conceptual area – negotiation strategies – combined with a strong focus on IND that both potentially hinder conceptual departures into other research directions.

2 Literature review

2.1 Cross-Cultural-Negotiation research

Cross-Cultural-Negotiations may be defined as an attempt to convince another party of one's own goals by means of communication, inhibited by different cultural frames. Research in this field extends back to the '60s of the last century, where it emerged as an independent string of negotiation research. Since then, myriads of studies, quantitative, qualitative, and conceptual had been published. Early research already assumed that national culture is an important factor in Cross-Cultural-Negotiations (Sawyer and Guetzkow 1965). Over the years, there emerged a growing body of evidence that culture plays a major role in Cross-Border-Negotiations (e.g., Brett et al. 2017, Gelfand et al. 2013, Adair et al. 2007, Elahee et al. 2002). There are different methodological strings in the literature of Cross-Cultural-Negotiation research. First, some publications developed their own comprehensive dimensional frameworks that relate to the nature of Cross-Cultural-Negotiations, but are independent of the influence of Hofstede and The Globe Study, e.g., Salacuse 1999 and Weiss and Stripp 1998. Secondly, there is research that uses dimensions that originate from Hofstede which are further developed, e.g., Hofstede's Individuality dimension has been divided into horizontal individualism and vertical individualism (Triandis and Gelfand 1998) that are addressed in Cross-Cultural-Negotiation research settings (Banai et al. 2014; Erkus and Banai 2011). Third, there is research that defined own research parameters and compared their findings with Hofstede's dimensions, which represent significant, non-significant, reproducible, non-reproducible, and partly contradicting results (e.g., Graham et al. 1994; Graham and Mintu-Wimsat 1997). And last, there are authors where Hofstede and The Globe Study form a conceptual base for research of Cross-Cultural-Negotiation phenomena. In sum, Cross-Cultural-Negotiation research represents an accumulation of valuable but single, i.e., not connected findings that lack a categorization into a larger framework.

2.2 Conceptual frameworks of culture: Hofstede and The Globe Study

Hofstede's framework and The Globe Study belong to the largest investigations that had been conducted in the field of cross-cultural-management. Hofstede polled in the 1970s in an intracompany research framework at IBM 117000 executives and derived four dimensions from 50 countries: IND (Individuality), PDI (Power Distance), MAS (Masculinity), UAV (Uncertainty Avoidance) (Hofstede 1980), and in a following study an additional fifth dimension from 23 countries: LTO (Long-Term-Orientation) (Hofstede and Bond 1988). Results point to significant national differences along the named dimensions. Mid of the 1990s, The Globe Study repeated and enhanced Hofstede's research approach, with more than 17000 polled executives in an intercompany research setting, balancing possible company culture and industry bias by including 951 companies from 3 different industries from 62 cultures in 59 countries. The Globe Study cumulated in 9 dimensions: G-AS (Assertiveness), G-PO (Performance Orientation), G-FO (Future Orientation), G-I-COLL (Institutional Collectivism), G-G-COLL (In-Group Collectivism), G-GE (Gender Egalitarianism), G-PDI (Power Distance), G-UAV (Uncertainty Avoidance), and G-HO (Humane Orientation) (House et al. 2004). Further, The Globe Study introduced the division between cultural values ("Should be") and practices ("As is") in its dimensions. In other words, how people claim they behave in certain situations - based on tacit values - and how they behave in reality - self-reported practice - is addressed by two different sets of questionnaire items (House et al. 2004). By this division, it is envisaged to reveal possible inconsistencies between cultural reality and cultural ideal providing research an additional tool for analysis (Mahadevan 2017).

Summarized, The Globe Study has continued, enhanced, and updated Hofstede's work by both scope and methodology (e.g., Earley 2006). Concerning the applicability of Hofstede and The Globe Study frameworks with respect to Cross-Cultural-Negotiations, there is a mixed image: Whereas The Globe Study refers sporadically in a wider context to negotiations (House et al. 2004), Hofstede's dimensions are considered of a preliminary nature, providing little guidance and should be viewed more as general considerations that cannot be transferred into practice. He recommended that empirical research should follow in this field in order to validate and detail his generic conclusions (Hofstede 1989).

2.3 Definitions

In this paper, findings in Cross-Cultural-Negotiation research literature that link to the dimensions of Hofstede and The Globe Study are displayed. Since both studies use partly the same dimensional nomenclature, some abbreviations are introduced to clearly distinguish the dimensions of the two cultural studies. The abbreviations are listed in the appendix (Table 8). Further, the notion "finding" in this paper is defined as research finding – i.e.,

significant findings of research or confirmed hypotheses - in Cross-Cultural-Negotiation literature that conceptual construct is based on a cultural dimension of Hofstede or The Globe Study.

3 Method

For this review, Cross-Cultural-Negotiation research literature had been systematically searched for findings that had been obtained using cultural dimensional constructs. There are several studies in cross-cultural research that delivered such constructs. This paper focuses on the two most prominent and largest studies: Hofstede's work and The Globe Study. Thus, only literature containing findings that referred to Hofstede and/ or The Globe Study was used. Following Rousseau et al. (2008), the goal of this review is to give an overview of the research landscape, create a synthesis, and identify contradicting findings that point to future avenues of research. For ensuring a systematic procedure, a methodological framework for this type of review as proposed by Macpherson and Jones (2010), Denyer and Tranfield (2008), Tranfield et al. (2003), Webster and Watson (2002), and Mulrow (1994) had been applied. To avoid possible author bias during the search, selection, and analysis process, a review protocol as advocated by Tranfield et al. (2003) had been created before the search process and operationalized meticulously in the process of this review.

3.1 Identification of literature

Before operationalizing the literature identification process, search words, combinations, and sources had been defined in the review protocol, as shown in Table 1. The search criteria had been the following: (1) Literature until the year 2017, including, has been used. (2) Only literature in the English language has been considered. (3) The search comprised academic journals, conference contributions, or published dissertations. Further, as advocated by Tranfield et al. (2003), the search also included Google Scholar, Google, and Researchgate.

The search has been operationalized using search words of two classifications: The primary search term group is subsumed under the main term of 'negotiation' and the secondary under the term of 'culture'. Synonyms of the search terms had been added, gathered from different thesauri. Concerning the second search term (culture), the dimensions of Hofstede (Five dimensions) and The Globe Study (Nine dimensions) had also been added. For the search, a combination of primary and secondary search terms, the boolean logic [AND] had been applied, as shown in Table 1. In continuation, a title and text search have been conducted.

Table 1 Search strings and sources

Primary search terms	Boolean logic	Secondary search terms	Journal Sources ^a
Negotiati*			Ann. Reviews Electronic Back Vol. Coll.
Bargaining			Blackw. Pub. Journ.Backfiles (Wiley Onl.)
Conflict			Business Searching
Agreement			Business Source Complete
	AND		Cambridge Journals Digital Archives
		Global	China Academic Journals
		Cultur*	Columbia International Affairs Onl.
		International	De Gruyter Online Journ. Archive
		Intercultur*	Directory of Open Access Journ. - DOAJ
		Cross-Cultur*	Ebook Central by ProQuest
		Hofstede	Ebsco eBook Collection
		Globe Study	Elsevier Journal Backfiles (ScienceDirect)
		Individualism	Emerald Fulltext Archive Database
		Power Distance	Google Scholar
		Long-Term Orientation	Google
		Uncertainty Avoidance	IMF eLibrary
		Masculinity	Nexis Uni
		Performance Orientation	OECD working paper series
		Collectivism	OECD.Stat
		Future Orientation	Oxford Journals Digital Archive
		Gender Egalitarianism	Oxford Scholarship Online
		Assertiveness	Periodicals Archive Online – PAO
		Humane Orientation	Research Gate
			Sage Journals Online
			ScienceDirect (Elsevier)
			Springer ebooks
			Springer Online Journal Archives
			Statista
			Taylor and Francis Online Archives
			University Press Scholarship Online
			World Bank E-Library Archive
			World Biographical Information System

^aThe search had been operationalized by the search engine on more databases than displayed. Only important and relevant databases are displayed in this overview

3.2 Selection of literature

As a result of the systematic search in the literature, a total of 476 publications had been identified. For the selection of findings, a two-step selection process following Becheikh et al. (2006) has been applied. The first step comprised the process of selection of literature. The inclusion criteria for the first step had been the following: (1) Only quantitative studies had been used, due to its clear defined quality criteria and possible issues that might occur during assessment and comparison of quantitative and qualitative studies, which is still subject to controversy discussions (e.g., Tranfield et al. 2003; Engel and Kuzel 1992). (2) Studies had been included with Hofstede or The Globe Study in the reference list.

In a second step, the findings of the identified literature had been analyzed and categorized into the four negotiation stages model of Adair and Brett (2005). Therefore following inclusion criteria had been applied: (1) Only findings of a positivistic nature with a supported hypothesis or significant research results had been considered for this review. (2) Clear attribution of the finding to a cultural dimensional construct of Hofstede or The Globe Study. Of in total of 476 identified publications, 69 were identified after the operationalization of step one and step two.

3.3 Findings categorization

In continuation, a findings synthesis has been operationalized, grouping the findings by categorization (Tranfield et al. 2003, Mulrow 1994) into one of the four negotiation stages as defined by Adair and Brett (2005): 1. Stage Relational positioning, 2. Stage Identifying the problem, 3. Stage Generating solutions, and 4. Reaching agreement. The categorization had been operationalized, creating a taxonomy of each finding and categorize it with it the appropriate negotiation stage using the given keywords on which the negotiation stages were attributed by the authors (Adair and Brett 2005). Thereafter from 69 publications, 113 findings of 39 publications could be categorized into the four stages framework. Findings that couldn't be categorized into one negotiation stage had been excluded from the analysis. A schematic depiction of the categorization and exclusion of findings is shown in Fig. 1 below. Concerning the foci analysis of the research field's sub-categories, the taxonomy of the finding analysis had been used and grouped by research subject. The result of this operationalization can be seen in Fig. 2.

4 Findings

4.1 Overview

The overview of the existing literature shows that the majority of the examined publications refer predominantly to Hofstede as a cultural model of reference (Table 2). In these publications, Hofstede eclipses The Globe Study by far with 105 research findings versus eight findings, i.e., Hofstede's dimensions account for 92,92% of the findings in this review. Considering the distribution of the referred dimensions within the studies as shown in Table 1, Hofstede's IND dimension dominates the dimensional findings with 82 findings in the Cross-Cultural-Negotiation literature that were categorized into the negotiation stages of Adair and Brett (2005), whereas PDI shows 15 findings, LTO 6, and MAS with two findings. Hofstede's UAV dimension was not represented with any findings within this review.

Fig. 1 Findings categorization scheme

The number of findings in the literature using The Globe Study framework as a conceptual construct of culture is as follows: G-AS three findings, G-G-COLL three findings, G-PDI one finding, G-UAV one finding, and G-HO one finding. To four dimensions of The Globe Study are not referred in the literature: G-FO, G-I-COLL, G-PO, and G-GE. Summarized the claim of Inman et al. (2014), Kirkman et al. (2006), Bazerman et al. (2000), and Leung (1997) that Hofstede's IND is the cultural dimension most referred to in Cross-Cultural-Negotiation research is confirmed. Unlike Hofstede's Individuality dimension, there is no predominant dimension of The Globe Study used in Cross-Cultural-Negotiations research. Further, the distribution of the dimensional findings of The Globe Study should be considered as a temporal snapshot only since each further publication might – due to the small number of studies – change this distribution significantly.

Hence these findings show that negotiation research lacks pluralism in two ways: First, there is lacking a more balanced distribution between Hofstede's work and The Globe Study, with Hofstede accounting for most of the findings in Cross-Cultural-Negotiation research. And, second, a more balanced distribution within the dimensions of both studies. Hofstede's IND dimension represents 72,57% of all findings displayed in this review. In Table 2 also the distribution of dimensional findings along the four stages of negotiation of Adair and Brett (2005) is shown. Focusing on the distribution of findings that could be categorized along the four negotiation stages, Stage 3 shows the highest aggregation of research findings. One should note that Stage 3 is most comprehensively attributed by the authors, where consequently, most findings could be categorized to (Adair and Brett 2005).

4.2 Findings – Negotiation Stages

In continuation, the findings of this literature review are displayed along the four negotiation stages as defined by Adair and Brett (2005). Important coherent findings were summarized and described in the text. The complete overview of findings can be seen in the tables appending each stage.

4.3 Negotiation Stage 1: Relational positioning

One attribute of negotiation stage one where findings are categorized with is competitive posturing and/ or relationship building (Adair and Brett 2005). Concerning competitive posturing, findings in Cross-Cultural-Negotiation research show that cultures with measured low IND scores dispose of more competitive aspirations (Aslani et al. 2016) and show a greater preference for engaging in competitive bargaining (Elahee et al. 2002). Hence, it may be questionable whether win/ win approaches, as defined by Fisher and Ury (Fisher and Ury 1981), promise greater joint gains universally.

Table 2 Number of findings in the literature using dimensions of Hofstede and The Globe Study as a conceptual construct

Negotiation Stage ^a	Hofstede Dimensions					The Globe Study Dimensions									Total per Stage
	IND	PDI	MAS	UAV	LTO	G-AS	G-PDI	G-G-COLL	G-I-COLL	G-GE	G-UAV	G-PO	G-FO	G-HO	
1	12	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	17
2	22	4	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	27
3	44	6	2	0	5	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	60
4	4	0	0	0	1	0	1	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	9
Total per Dimension	82	15	2	0	6	3	1	2	0	0	1	0	0	1	113
% per Dimension	72,57%	13,27%	1,77%	0,00%	5,31%	2,65%	0,88%	1,77%	0,00%	0,00%	0,88%	0,00%	0,00%	0,88%	

^aNegotiation stages according to Adair and Brett (2005): (1) Relational Positioning; (2) Identifying the Problem; (3) Generating Solutions; (4) Reaching Agreement

4.3.1 Relationship building in Cross-Cultural-Negotiations

Concerning relationship building, there are no findings in Cross-Cultural-Negotiation research that connect to Hofstede or The Globe Study, which point to a cultural tendency directly whether or to which degree relationships are more or less valued by certain cultures. However, some findings are indirectly connected to this question of how much emphasis is put on relationship building. Cultures low on IND seem to spend more time on relationship building (Vieregge and Quick 2011) and show a higher likelihood to endorse a pro-relationship mindset with in-group members under high accountability (Liu et al. 2012). Further findings show that the distinction of in-group respectively out-group for high IND cultures seems to be of minor importance since for these cultures, a higher propensity to negotiate with strangers has been measured (Ready and Tessema 2009).

Those findings on the IND continuum match with the finding of Hofstede, where low IND score cultures are associated with a stronger distinction of in-group/ out-group status that impedes relationship building with strangers (Hofstede 2001). Once relationships are established, however, low IND cultures tend to show less legalism (Lin and Miller 2003) and a higher tendency to exchange off-task information compared to high IND cultures (Graf 2010). This finding harbors an opportunity for high IND negotiators seeking integrative agreements. Establishing a working relationship seems to change the behavior of low IND negotiators that reduces legal blocking, and eases cooperative agreements with low IND counterparts. A further characteristic of this negotiation stage is how influence is exerted concerning status and power. Research has found a prevalence of cultures high in PDI, acknowledging power as a means of influence (Brett and Okumura 1998; Kopelman et al. 2016). This is supported by the finding of Graham et al. (1988) that the difference of buyer/ seller profits are a function of status importance in high PDI cultures, with buyers achieving higher profits than sellers, and by the finding of Tinsley (1998) that conflict resolution taking place by deferring to status power.

4.3.2 Affective persuasion in Cross-Cultural-Negotiations

Another attribute of the first negotiation stage is affective persuasion that is defined as influence based on status and relationships (Adair and Brett 2004). Measures of affective influence are, for example, the use of threats or appeals to sympathy (Adair and Brett 2004). Collectivistic cultures, i.e., with low measured IND scores, show these characteristics more strongly (Aslani et al. 2016), as well as low IND cultures that use these relational factors as key motivators (Tse et al. 1994). A complimentary finding concerning this subject is that time spent on persuasion seems to be greater on high IND cultures compared to cultures low on IND (Vieregge Quick 2011). In summary, this first negotiation stage is dominated by findings related to Hofstede's work exclusively, with a majority of findings associated with its IND dimension, containing five findings that link to the PDI dimension.

Table 3 Findings in Negotiation Stage 1

Dim. Value	Findings of Study	Reference
Low - IND	Higher tendency of using Influence in Negotiation	Aslani et al. 2016
Low - IND	Higher inclination of using relational elements as key motivators, i.e. impress and influence the other party	Tse et al. 1994
High - PDI	Higher buyer profits as function of status importance	Graham 1988
High - PDI	Higher difference of buyer-seller profits as a function of status importance	Graham 1988
High - PDI	Larger preference of conflict resolution by deferring to status power	Tinsley 1998
Low - IND	Greater competitive aspirations	Aslani et al., 2016
Low - IND	Greater preference for engaging in competitive bargaining	Elahee et al., 2002
Low - IND	Sellers use a lower percentage of presumptive information about buyers	Roemer et al. 1999
High - IND	Higher relative power leads to a lower degree of a compromising negotiation approach	Lin and Miller 2003
High - PDI	More focus on power in preparation sessions	Brett and Okumura 1998
High - PDI	Higher susceptibility to power asymmetries in negotiations	Kopelman et al. 2016
High - IND	Higher comfort negotiating with a stranger	Ready and Tessema 2009
Low - IND	Relationship commitment leads to less legalism	Lin and Miller 2003
Low - IND	More time spent on rapport	Vieregge and Quick 2011
Low - IND	More exchange of off-task information	Graf et al. 2010
Low - IND	Higher likelihood to endorse a pro-relationship mindset in negotiations with in-group members under high accountability	Liu et al. 2012
High - IND	More time spent on persuasion	Vieregge and Quick 2011

Interpretation example: "Low-IND" – "Higher Tendency of using influence in negotiation": Low-Hofstede Individuality dimension cultures (i.e., collectivistic cultures) show a higher tendency of using influence in negotiation

4.4. Negotiation Stage 2: Identifying the Problem

The second negotiation stage is dominated by two important factors: Getting information about the other party's preferences and priorities by reciprocal information exchange and building trust (Adair and Brett 2005).

4.4.1 Information exchange in Cross-Cultural-Negotiations

Findings show that there seems to be an apparent dichotomy in shaped cultural approaches of how to exchange information. This dichotomy appears to stretch-out along Hofstede's IND scale. Direct information exchange is understood as the concept of communication that one party asks direct questions, the other party responds, and vice-versa (Adair and Brett 2004). Aslani et al. (2016), Adair and Brett (2004), and Brett et al. (1998) found a higher preference for direct information exchange in cultures with high IND scores. On the other hand, information exchange seems to be understood differently in cultures with low IND scores. Here information exchange is defined as an indirect approach using patterns and configurations of written offers that are exchanged as information (Adair and Brett 2004). Adair and Brett (2004), Adair et al. (2001), and Adair (1999) found a preference for the use and reciprocation of indirect information exchange in cultures with low IND scores.

Ambiguous findings were found concerning the question of whether the exchange of integrative information is preferred by certain cultures. Brett and Okumura found them to be ascribed to high IND cultures (Brett and Okumura 1998), whereas the finding of Graf et al. (2010) shows the contrary for interfirm electronic negotiations: More exchange of integrative information in cultures low on IND.

One possible explanation might be the existence of different interpretations of the term "integrative information". Following the conception of Fons Trompenaars (Trompenaars and Hampden-Turner 1997) where universal words, for example, "integrative information" finds support in many cultures, but differ in the way how they are interpreted. In other words, getting valuable information about the other priorities may be supported in most cultures around the globe, but whether this is done via reciprocal question and answering or by the design of offers without exchanging important verbal information across the table is subject to cultural frames. Bearing in mind that the lower end of the IND scale is mostly populated by countries of "non-western regions", i.e., Latin-America, Asia, and Africa (Hofstede 2001), where getting information of the other parties' priorities might be associated with non-direct information exchange, as shown, for example, by Adair et al. (2007) for Japan.

Therefore it is not surprising that - expanding above findings - in low IND and high PDI score cultures, the exchange of early offers represent the process of information gathering, whereas, in cultures high on IND and low on PDI scores, early offers reflect information consolidation (Adair et al. 2007). What for one culture, an offer is a medium of information exchange -Low IND-, is for other cultures the outcome of the process -High IND. Further

findings relate to this phenomenon by showing measurable impacts on joint gains, where higher information exchange before first offers increases joint gains in high IND cultures and decreases it in cultures low on IND (Adair et al. 2007). This finding might also question the general applicability of the Harvard Method (Fisher and Ury 1981), where the authors advocate direct question and answer to achieve joint gains universally.

4.4.2 Trust building in Cross-Cultural-Negotiations

Another important aspect of the second negotiation stage is trust. Trust belongs to the most important aspects of negotiations (Gunia et al. 2012). There seem to exist different factors on which trust is based. One factor described in research is external trust, i.e., basing trust on legal systems, contracts, litigation, and law enforcement (Metcalf et al. 2007). According to this definition, many dimensional findings in the literature related to Hofstede and The Globe Study support external trust patterns: High scores on G-AS and IND, low on PDI (Metcalf et al. 2007). Summarized, in the second negotiation stage, there was found a similar spread of dimensional distribution in the findings as in the first negotiation stage, i.e., Hofstede's IND dimension mostly dominating, but also containing one finding that links to The Globe Study. As it has been shown, Hofstede's IND dimension leads in negotiation stage two to the contradicting result of the exchange of integrative information that results in an avenue for future research.

Table 4 Findings in Negotiation Stage 2

Dim. Value	Findings of Study	Reference
High-IND	Higher likelihood of use of direct information exchange	Adair et al. 2004
Low-IND	Higher likelihood of use of indirect information exchange	Adair et al. 2004
High-IND	More use of direct information exchange	Adair et al. 2001
Low-IND	More use of indirect information exchange	Adair et al. 2001
Low-IND	Early offers reflect information gathering	Adair et al. 2007
High-IND	Higher information exchange before first offer increase joint gains	Adair et al. 2007
Low-IND	Higher information exchange before first offer decrease joint gains	Adair et al. 2007
High-IND	More information exchange	Aslani et al. 2016
High-IND	More information exchange	Brett et al. 1998
High-IND	Higher integrative "information flow"	Brett and Okumura 1998
Low-IND	Request for more information	Cai et al. 2000
Low-IND	Decrease of buyer giving directional information	Cai et al. 2000
Low-IND	More exchange of integrative information	Graf et al. 2010
High-IND	More reciprocation of direct information sharing	Adair 1999
Low-IND	More reciprocation of indirect information sharing	Adair 1999
High-IND	Lower effect of cooperative reciprocation	Mintu et al. 2011
Low-IND	Exchanging less information before making first offer	Adair et al. 2007
High-IND	Early offers reflect information consolidation	Adair et al. 2007
High-PDI	Exchanging less information before making first offer	Adair et al. 2007
Low-PDI	Early offers reflect information consolidation	Adair et al. 2007
High-PDI	Early offers reflect information gathering	Adair et al. 2007
High-G-AS	Bases of trust - External	Metcalf et al. 2007

Low-IND	Greater preference for placing more trust in a negotiator from their own country than from a foreign country	Elahee et al., 2002
High-IND	Bases of trust - External	Metcalf et al. 2007
Low-IND	Higher likelihood of success with an apology after integrity-based trust violation	Maddux et al. 2011
Low-IND	Higher likelihood that an apology leads to more with trusting intentions after an integrity-based trust violation	Maddux et al. 2011
Low-PDI	Bases of trust - External	Metcalf et al. 2007

Interpretation example: "High-IND" – "Higher likelihood of use of direct information exchange": High-Hofstede Individuality dimension cultures show a higher likelihood of the use of direct information exchange.

4.5 Negotiation Stage 3: Generating solutions

Concurring with the relatively wide definition of attributes on which Adair and Brett (2005) characterize this negotiation stage, consequently, most findings – compared to the other three stages - are attributed to it.

4.5.1 First offers in Cross-Cultural-Negotiations

One central attribute of negotiation stage three is the issue of first offers. First Offers is a strong predictor of joint gains (Galinsky and Mussweiler 2001). Findings indicate that there are cultures that seem to be more likely to make early first offers: Cultures showing low IND and high PDI scores (Adair et al. 2007). Concerning the effect of first offers, there is an interesting association with the finding that first offers predict economic gains for high IND cultures (Ma et al. 2002). Linking this finding with the issue of first offers as a means of information exchange¹ - see stage two -, further evidence provided that the longer the parties take to issues first offers joint gains are increased in high IND cultures, due to possible additional information, and reduced in low IND cultures, due to missing information since less information is transferred (Adair et al. 2007).

Summarized, first offers have different effects along the continuum of the Hofstede's IND scale. Consequently, applying the Harvard Method universally (Fisher and Ury 1981) - with its proposed reciprocal information exchange will likely lead to a delayed issue of first offers – and hence reduce the probability of joint gains in negotiations with low IND cultures (Adair et al. 2007). As conceived in the definition of Adair and Brett, 'information exchange' resides in stage two and 'first offers' in stage three. These findings show that the cultural interpretations of these two subjects seem to be intertwined and not clearly separable. Hence, first offers and information exchange should not be viewed separately but rather regarded as a connected phenomenon for low IND cultures. Another important characteristic of negotiation stage three is the value claiming phase. Research has

¹ In the stage attribution of Adair and Brett (2005) information exchange resides in stage 2 and first offers in stage 3. As later published work of Adair et al. (2007) shows that information exchange and first offers can not be clearly separated for cultures low on IND. Adhering to the original definition, first offers and information exchange stretches in this review from negotiation stage 2 to negotiation stage 3.

investigated whether there is a cultural preference following egoistic or altruistic motives in claiming value. Gelfand and Christakopoulous (1999) found that high IND score cultures prefer claiming more value for themselves compared to low IND cultures that tend to consider more the other side's interests (Gelfand and Christakopoulous 1999; Graf et al. 2010).

4.5.2 Competitive vs. Cooperative negotiation strategies

The next characteristic of the third negotiation stage research findings could be associated with is the application of competitive versus cooperative negotiation strategies. Previous literature suggested that it might be questionable whether low-IND cultures tend to adopt cooperative strategies, and high-IND cultures favor competitive approaches (Snir 2014; Mintu-Wimsat and Madjourova-Davri 2011). Concerning this question, the literature shows a mixed image: There are findings for low IND cultures that indicate a preference for competitive strategies (Brett et al. 1998), in particular for sellers if the buyer is of low IND provenience (Cai et al. 2000), whereas high IND cultures use cooperative strategies by a higher likelihood (Liu 2011; Baber and Ojala 2015). On the other hand, there are findings that show evidence for the opposite: High IND cultures are more likely to adopt forcing and legalism - a competitive strategy (Lin and Miller 2003), and Low IND cultures tend with a higher likelihood to cooperative strategies (Mintu-Wimsat and Madjourova-Davri 2011; Lin and Miller 2003; Snir 2014). Therefore Hofstede's IND dimension seems to have little meaning with respect to this topic. However, there are several findings that link to other dimensions of Hofstede and The Globe Study that could help to provide more information: A higher likelihood for a competitive approach is associated with low G-HO (Lügger et al. 2014), high PDI (Brett and Okumura 1998), high MAS (Metcalf et al. 2007), and high G-AS cultures (Metcalf et al. 2007). This is contradicted by the findings of Lügger for low G-AS cultures where a competitive strategy is more likely to be adopted (Lügger et al. 2014).² Further, there is more evidence that PDI plays a role in the preferences for competitive or cooperative negotiation strategies. High PDI cultures embrace more power and influence - a competitive strategy - than low PDI cultures (Adair et al. 2001; Tinsley 2001). This suggests that the adoption of a competitive or cooperative negotiation strategy can't be explained by Hofstede's IND dimension only. The use of additional dimensions of both Hofstede and The Globe Study may help to shed further light on this phenomenon.

² The authors speak of a distributive strategy; however, in this context, distributive and competitive are viewed as synonymous in this review.

4.5.3 Problem-solving approach and its reciprocation in Cross-Cultural-Negotiations

Another well-investigated aspect of negotiation strategy is the use of problem solving approaches that are likely to occur in the following cultures: High PDI (Graham et al. 1994), high LTO (Graham and Mintu-Wimsat 1997; Graham et al. 1994), low in IND (Graham et al. 1994; Mintu-Wimsat and Madjourova-Davri 2011; Snir 2014), a finding that is contradicted by results of Baber, et al. (2015) and Lin and Miller (2003) linking the prevalent use of problem solving approaches to high IND cultures, which shows an ambiguity of the preference of problem solving strategies along the IND continuum. A similar ambiguity of results is also found when tested whether negotiators' problem-solving approach is reciprocated by the other side. A higher likelihood of reciprocation for low IND cultures is shown by Adler et al. (1992) but contradicted by the finding of Liu (2011), showing a higher likelihood of reciprocity for high IND cultures. Due to this ambiguity of both - i.e., problem-solving approach and its reciprocation - it is recommendable to refrain from using IND in both contexts until future research will have provided clarification.

4.5.4 Power persuasion strategies in Cross-Cultural-Negotiations

Another strategic element that seems to be subject to a differentiated application around the globe is the use of power persuasion strategies. Along the PDI continuum, cultures with high PDI seem to favor power persuasion strategies (Tinsley 2001). This plausible result is contradicted by the finding that U.S. - characterized by low PDI/ High IND - seems to embrace the concept of BATNA as power more than the Japanese - High PDI/ Low IND - (Brett and Okumura 1998). Hence, the dimension of PDI seems not to explain the preference for the use of the concept of power alone, rather in combination with Hofstede's IND dimension. Another element of displaying power is supported by the finding that forcing and legalism approaches are more immanent to high IND cultures, whereas using compromising strategies are ascribed to low IND cultures (Lin and Miller 2003). Indirectly connected to this finding is that high IND cultures show a higher preference for the time spent on compromises (Viergege and Quick 2011). Also, other strategical positioning approaches are associated with the LTO as well as with the IND dimension: Task-oriented approaches, as characterized by "get the deal and move on" has been attributed to high IND and high LTO cultures opposed by the strategy "secure an ally, develop the relationship" which is found to be immanent in low IND and low LTO cultures (Baber and Ojala 2015). Further, possible cultural adaptability to the other parties strategy was investigated: Is there a culture that shows a higher trend to adapt to others' cultural strategy? Findings confirm that cultures with low IND scores seem to adapt more to the other parties' strategy compared to cultures high in IND (Snir 2014).

Table 5 Findings in Negotiation Stage 3

Dim. Value	Findings of Study	Reference
High-G-AS	Higher degree of distributive negotiation behavior	Metcalf et al. 2007
Low-G-AS	Higher likelihood of use of distributive tactics	Lügger et al. 2014
High-G-HO	Higher likelihood of use of integrative behavior	Lügger et al. 2014
Low-IND	Higher positive effect on own reported cooperative problem-solving behaviors	Mintu et al. 2011
Low-IND	Greater use of cooperative problem solving	Mintu et al. 2011
Low-IND	Higher likelihood of adoption of distributive tactics	Brett et al. 1998
Low-IND	Seller use less distributive tactics	Cai et al. 2000
Low-IND	Buyer use more distributive tactics	Cai et al. 2000
High-IND	Higher probability of use of distributive transformational sequences	Liu 2011
High-IND	Higher probability of use of integrative transformational sequences	Liu 2011
High-IND	Higher probability of use of integrative reciprocity	Liu 2011
Low-IND	Higher use of problem-solving approach	Graham et al. 1994
High-IND	View of self-oriented behaviors as more appropriate	Tinsley and Pillutla 1998
High-IND	View of joint problem solving as more appropriate	Tinsley and Pillutla 1998
Low-IND	View of equality-oriented behaviors as more appropriate	Tinsley and Pillutla 1998
Low-IND	Negotiators problem-solving approach leads to partners problem-solving approach	Adler et al. 1992
High-LTO	Higher tendency towards a problem-solving approach	Graham and Mintu-Wimsat 1997
High-LTO	Higher tendency towards a problem solving approach	Graham et al. 1994
High-MAS	Higher likelihood of distributive negotiation behavior	Metcalf et al. 2007
High-PDI	Higher likelihood of distributive tactics	Brett and Okumura 1998
High-PDI	Higher tendency towards a problem solving approach	Graham et al. 1994
Low-IND	Increased time duration to make first offer reduces joint gains	Adair et al. 2007
High-IND	Increased time duration to make first offer increases joint gains	Adair et al. 2007
Low-IND	More perception of fairness of the other negotiators offer	Gelfand, et al., 2002
Low-IND	Higher perception of integrative negotiation leads to less extreme first offers	Ma and Jaeger 2010
High-IND	First offers predict economic gains	Ma and Jaeger 2010
High-IND	Level of first offers is positively related to assertiveness	Ma and Jaeger 2010
Low-IND	Higher likelihood of making earlier first offers	Adair et al. 2007
High-PDI	Higher likelihood of making earlier first offers	Adair et al. 2007
Low-IND	Higher propensity of reciprocation of power-based influence	Adair 1999
High-PDI	Higher likelihood of use power and influence	Adair et al. 2001
Low-IND	More task orientated in negotiations	Metcalf et al. 2007
Low-LTO	Higher Negotiators' individual profits when problem solving approach is used	Graham and Mintu-Wimsat 1997
Low-MAS	Problem Solving Approach leads to partners satisfaction with agreements	Graham and Mintu-Wimsat 1997
High-IND	Higher likelihood of use of negotiation strategy "Explore/Solve - Win/Win"	Baber and Ojala 2015
High-IND	Higher likelihood of use of negotiation strategy "Logrolling"	Baber and Ojala 2015
High-IND	Higher use of problem solving approach	Lin and Miller 2003
Low-IND	Higher use of compromise approach	Lin and Miller 2003

High-IND	More time spent on compromise	Vierregge and Quick 2011
High-IND	Higher likelihood to use forcing and legalism in negotiations	Lin and Miller 2003
High-IND	Higher probability of use of distributive complementary negotiation strategy	Liu 2011
High-IND	Higher probability of use of integrative complementary negotiation strategy	Liu 2011
Low-IND	Increased trend to use integrative negotiation strategy	Snir 2014
Low-IND	Increased trend to adapt more to the opposites strategy	Snir 2014
High-IND	Higher probability of use of negotiation strategy "Get the deal and move on"	Baber and Ojala 2015
Low-IND	Higher probability of use of negotiation strategy "Secure an ally, develop the relationship"	Baber and Ojala 2015
Low-IND	Higher competitive goals lead to greater distributive reciprocity	Liu 2011
Low-IND	Higher counterparts competitive goals leads to increase of distributive complementary sequences	Liu 2011
Low-IND	Higher likelihood to use ethically questionable strategies	Ma 2010
High-IND	Men show higher use of ethically questionable strategies compared to women	Ma 2010
Low-IND	More adjustment of behavior in negotiations if high power distance prevails	Kopelman et al. 2016
High-IND	High power managers raise expectations of less cooperation after face to face discussion with low power others	Kopelman et al. 2016
High-IND	Higher use of interest strategy	Tinsley 2001
High-LTO	Higher probability of use of Negotiation Strategy "Get the deal and move on"	Baber and Ojala 2015
Low-LTO	Higher probability of use of Negotiation Strategy "Secure an ally, develop the relationship"	Baber and Ojala 2015
High-PDI	Higher use of power persuasion strategy	Tinsley 2001
Low-PDI	Embracing more the concept of BATNA as power	Brett and Okumura 1998
High-IND	Embracing more the concept of BATNA as power	Brett and Okumura 1998
High-IND	Claim more value for themselves	Gelfand and Christakopoulous 1999
High-IND	Claiming more value	Graf et al. 2010

Interpretation example: "High-G-AS" – "Higher degree of distributive negotiation behavior": High-Globe-Assertiveness dimension cultures show a higher degree of distributive negotiation behavior.

Following strategic approaches, the parties in negotiation stage three start influencing the outcome. Not surprising that findings show that high PDI cultures are more likely to use power and influence (Adair et al. 2001), and low IND cultures show a high probability of reciprocating power-based influence attempts (Adair 1999). Again these findings suggest that power might be a concept that stretches out beyond the PDI dimension. Especially in negotiations where the negotiating parties show both as a cultural characteristic - high PDI and low IND - there might be a higher likelihood that power influence and reciprocation spirals might end-up in a negotiation deadlock or a possible break-off of negotiations. Summarized, the findings of stage three show again high domination of Hofstede's dimensional framework and especially of its IND dimension with only marginal findings of LTO, PDI, and singular findings attributed to G-AS and the G-HO dimension. This stage also shows limitations of Hofstede's IND dimension in three areas: First, as a predictor of competitive or cooperative negotiation strategies, second, problem-solving approaches, and third, the reciprocation of problem-solving approaches. Further, contradictory findings concerning the use of power persuasion strategies had been found delivered by the use of Hofstede's PDI dimension.

4.6. Negotiation Stage 4: Reaching agreement

4.6.1 Decision making in Cross-Cultural-Negotiations

In negotiation stage four, both parties move forward to close the deal: The final agreement is prepared, and decisions are made whether to accept or reject final offers. Cross-cultural-research already pointed to differences in decision-making processes around the globe, mainly along the IND and G-I-COLL scales (Hofstede 2001; House et al. 2004). Negotiation research found a higher likelihood of decisions made by consensus in negotiations in high G-G-COLL and low G-PDI cultures (Metcalf et al. 2006). Before the closure of negotiations, multiple interests are packed into multi-issue offers. According to the findings of Tinsley and Brett (2001), high IND cultures show a higher prevalence of connecting multiple interests that result in multiple offers than low IND cultures.

4.6.2 Time pressure in Cross-Cultural-Negotiations

Before concluding, negotiations parties may face deadlines, given by external circumstances. On the one hand, there are parties more or less susceptible to time pressure. Here Salmon et al. (2016) confirmed the plausible assumption that low LTO cultures view time as more condensed, making them more prone to time pressure. Further, there are cultures that are more likely to exert time pressure on the other party. Findings show that the use of time pressure is favored by the following cultures: High IND, low G-G-COLL, and high G-UAV (Saorín-Iborra

and Cubillo 2016). In this final stage, The Globe Study shows a higher share of findings compared to the other three stages, however with Hofstede still as the dominating study but showing a more balanced mix in the use of his dimensions.

Table 6 Findings in Negotiation Stage 4

Dim. Value	Findings of Study	Reference
High-IND	Higher prevalence of synthesizing multiple interests	Tinsley and Brett 2001
Low-IND	Sellers making single offers positively associated to buyers collectivism	Cai et al. 2000
Low-IND	Packaging multiple offers by seller positively associated with collectivism	Cai et al. 2000
High-G-G-COLL	More Consensus Team Orientation	Metcalf et al. 2006
Low-G-PDI	More Consensus Team Orientation	Metcalf et al. 2006
High-IND	Higher likelihood of use of time pressure	Saorín-Iborra and Cubillo 2016
G-G-COLL	Greater use of time pressure	Saorín-Iborra and Cubillo 2016
High-LTO	View of time as more condensed	Salmon et al. 2016
G-UAV	Greater use of time pressure	Saorín-Iborra and Cubillo 2016

Interpretation example: "High-IND" – "Higher prevalence of synthesizing multiple interests": High-Hofstede Individuality dimension cultures show a higher prevalence of synthesizing multiple interests.

4.7 Focus on one research fields' sub-category: Negotiation strategies

In order to provide a deeper insight into Cross-Cultural-Negotiation research, an analysis of the research foci of the research fields' sub-categories has been carried out, providing a holistic view of the landscape of research. This sheds light on topics that had been in the center of attention as well as on those that were widely ignored so far. The graphical overview shows the research focus of the Cross-Cultural-Negotiation research sub-categories and below the corresponding number of research findings pointing to the cultural dimension. It is shown that negotiation strategies and, to a lesser extent, the nature of information exchange had been at the center of attention of research. Compared to these areas, only marginal attention had been paid to the following topics: Preparation of final agreements, susceptibility to negotiation deadlines, use of rational influence, affective persuasion, first offers, power influenced negotiation behavior, and relationship building. Within the main streams of research, Hofstede's IND dimension is predominantly used in the sub-categories displayed in this review. However, other dimensions are only marginally represented compared to IND, as the subject of negotiation strategies shows. Besides a very strong focus on IND, a relatively large diversity of dimensions is used, even though on small numbers. Other research subjects, e.g., information exchange, relationship building, power influenced negotiation behavior, and first offers lack this diversity.

Fig. 2: Number of findings per cultural dimension and research topic

^aThe underlined description represents the research field under which the findings were summarized. The thickness of the lines is associated with the number of findings that are attributed to the cultural dimension. For visualisation purpose, one 'pt' of line thickness equals one linked research finding. For the purpose of clarity, the number of findings is also included.

5 Discussion and future avenues of research

5.1 Methodological Limitations

This publication disposes of several limitations, given by the nature of this review. First, it embraces the largest quantitative cross-cultural studies. Therefore Hofstede and The Globe Study were addressed but omitting other cultural studies. Concerning the collection of findings, this review does not represent the complete picture of Cross-Cultural-Negotiation research, rather than the proportion of research that links to Hofstede and The Globe Study. Another limitation of this review is given by the fact that several findings could not be categorized into the negotiation stages framework of Adair and Brett (2005). Based on the definition in the research protocol, the findings had to be attributable to one of the four negotiation stages. Some findings, however, showed a too general definition, as, e.g., communication in negotiations that rather represents a meta-level, i.e., is used in all four stages, than being able to be categorized to one certain stage. These findings had been sorted into a findings exclusion scheme accordingly (Fig. 1).

Secondly, this review is indirectly exposed to the general issue that all cross-cultural research faces – its unclear definition of “culture” that is also inherent to the findings of this review. The notion of “culture” in negotiation research is mostly implicitly understood as “national culture”. However, there are other facets of culture that influence individuals that are rarely addressed by research: For example, organizational cultures that besides national culture, do independently exist (Hofstede 1985), „reflect the societies in which they are embedded“ (House et al. 2004 p.37), and also need to be considered when investigating culture (Kale 1996). Most studies in the research field do not consider this variable, which limits this review. Another limitation in this context is that research often misses addressing regional cultures. This cultural aspect, however, poses an important element in Cross-Cultural-Research, where findings show significant differences in the regions within a country (House et al. 2004). In contrast to Hofstede’s framework, The Globe Study addresses this variable, albeit on a small scale. Due to the ample use of Hofstede by research, this review mainly reflects the limited larger ‚national‘ view of the cultural world map, omitting a relatively finer gradation that The Globe Study would offer. A similar situation exists for professional, educational, and department culture, variables that also influence an individual’s behavior in negotiations, which are rarely part of experimental research settings or questionnaire designs. Also, the dynamics of culture - i.e., the continuous evolution of cultures over time - represents a further limitation. In other words, data of studies conducted at different periods that originate from similar or identical conceptual approaches nevertheless capture different snapshots of culture over time. Such an evolution is rarely controlled for in research designs and hence provides limited comparability of the findings in this review. The same applies to the comparability among the findings that link to Hofstede or The Globe Study. Both studies were

also collected at different periods, moreover using different methodologies and partly different dimensions. Therefore, the sorted findings of this review should not be combined, exchanged, or mixed between the two studies. Further, the notion of culture is often conceptualized by research as a bipolar continuum, as, e.g., the Individualism – Collectivism continuum, that links to the methodological approach of Hofstede or The Globe Study. Findings resulting from this methodology are frequently interpreted in a way that one country falls either on the Individualism or Collectivism side of the continuum, ignoring the gradations between the two poles within a cultural dimension. However, culture is a far more complex construct to be captured by a one-dimensional approach alone. Every culture is a cumulation of different characteristics that may be more comprehensively described using several dimensions. To display a culture with all its specific characteristics, Triandis (1982 p.88, 1983 pp.142-143) argues that an amount of 20 dimensions may be appropriate. In most publications, however, research approaches are designed to conceptionally depart using a relatively small number of dimensions or sometimes one dimension only. This limits not only the validity of its findings concerning the definition of culture but also the comparability of the findings within this review.

Another limitation is that besides culture, negotiators are also influenced by contextual factors. Such factors are, e.g., the role, the negotiation venue, or the negotiators' perception of each other. This holds especially true for cross-border negotiations, where negotiators' cognition of contextual situations is influenced by different cultural lenses. For example, Graham (1983) shows significant differences in negotiation outcomes influenced by negotiator roles (Buyer/ Seller) for the Japanese, but not for U.S. negotiators. Further, Drake (2001) found that the contextual effects of the role (Buyer/ Seller) influence negotiators more strongly than culture. Concerning the influence of perception of the negotiation partner Graham and Mintu-Wimsat (1997) show that negotiator attractiveness has a mixed impact on the negotiation partners' satisfaction around the world and hence can not be generalized. A similar situation exists for other than verbal communication, which is important to control for since it underlines, contradicts, or mitigates what has been said. This type of communication is also interpreted by different cultural lenses and hence especially important in Cross-Cultural-Negotiations. One example of how contextual factors of communication in negotiation affect research findings show Adair et al. (2007) that found that first offers in negotiations act as a means of communication in the Japanese, but not in the U.S. culture.

Also, external factors, as – for example - the existing BATNA or the information available about the other side, influences a negotiator's behavior. Comparable external factors are rarely included in research designs across different studies that limit the comparability of the studies conducted in the field, as well as a negotiator's personality that influences negotiations significantly. Finally, the existence of numerical results gathered by research that links to Hofstede and The Globe Study should not lead to the conclusion that these metrics predict a

negotiator's behavior alone, but rather in combination with contextual factors and especially the negotiator's personality.

5.2 Findings and future avenues of research

The use of cultural dimensions found large application in Cross-Cultural-Negotiation research. Many publications use two main constructs of culture, namely Hofstede's seminal work and The Globe Study, as the conceptual underpinning of their research. This review collected and sorted findings in Cross-Cultural-Negotiation research providing two main contributions: First, it addressed the absence of a large systematic framework that categorizes the findings in research that point to Hofstede's work (Metcalf and Bird 2004, Graham 1994), and, second, it addressed the demand of Gunia and Gelfand (2016) providing a holistic view of the state of Cross-Cultural-Negotiation research by incorporating The Globe Study into one common framework. As a result, this overview offers several points of critique.

5.2.1 Lacking pluralism: One-sided perspective on Hofstede's IND dimension

First, Hofstede and The Globe Study frameworks deliver in a total of fourteen dimensions as a potential conceptual basis for cross-cultural-negotiation research. However, this variety of dimensions has not found application in research yet and is being concentrated on mainly one framework with one dominating dimension. Inman et al. (2014); Kirkman et al. (2006); Bazerman et al. (2000), and Leung (1997) already speculated that Hofstede's IND dimension might be the most used in negotiation research. This literature review confirms this assumption and shows that research is lacking pluralism by putting this one-sided focus on Hofstede's IND dimension, as Hofstede's Individuality dimension accounts for 72,57% of all dimensions gathered in this review. Even when regarding the distribution within the Hofstede dimensional framework, its IND dimension offers an unproportioned high share of 78,10% of usage by Cross-Cultural-Negotiation research. Hence, it can be confidently claimed that the abundant use of IND creates a one-sided perspective onto Cross-Cultural-Negotiations, which probably leads to a distorted perspective or bias with respect to the diversity of the research field.

5.2.2 Abundant potential - Scarce use of alternative dimensional constructs

The next most referred cultural dimensions following IND are in descending order: PDI (13,27%), LTO (5,31%), MAS (1,77%), and UAV with no finding within this review. This opens up an avenue for future research investigating Cross-Cultural-Negotiation behavior in conjunction with the named Hofstede's dimensions except for IND. The inclusion of the MAS and especially the UAV dimension of Hofstede's framework into future

research might be promising since the use of these dimensions could enable new perspectives onto culture in negotiations. The use of MAS could contribute to the perspective on decision-making processes and problem solving approaches in negotiations (Hofstede 2001). Whereas UAV could contribute to future research investigating the effects of risk aversion and task versus relationship orientation in Cross-Cultural-Negotiations (Hofstede 2001). With respect to The Globe Study, the G-AS and the G-G-COLL dimensions are the most referred dimensions. Comparing Hofstede's work with The Globe Study, one would assume that the Individualism/Collectivism continuum would also be prominent within the dimensional distribution of The Globe Study. However, G-G-COLL merely shows three findings, and G-I-COLL is not referred at all in the literature. Especially the inclusion of G-I-COLL would be important since it represents – compared to G-G-COLL – a stronger orientation onto economic situations. Its questionnaire items addressed a higher share of economic-related scenarios where the dimension is based upon, whereas the G-G-COLL dimension is mainly based on a questionnaire construct that is centered upon family values (House et al. 2004, p.463).

Further, the use of The Globe Study dimensions also houses analytical potential for research in Cross-Cultural-Negotiations. The Globe Study shows with its division of cultural values and practice scores significant differences in various countries that also potentially exist in Cross-Cultural-Negotiations. These differences may be interpreted as the unspoken desire for an action in negotiation - value scores - and the action itself - practice scores (House et al. 2004 p. 98, Schein 1992 p. 16-17). As shown in a research setting in Cross-Cultural-Management by Mahadevan (2013), this dichotomic nature of The Globe Study dimensions can be used as an approach to bridge the gap between the positivist and interpretive research paradigm. This differentiation may help to mitigate the blurry definition of culture by giving research an analytical instrument to further explain a negotiator's behavior (Mahadevan 2017). Examples of application in Cross-Cultural-Negotiation research are shown by authors adopting The Globe Study's dimensions and its practice/ values scores: Sharma et al. (2017) and Metcalf et al. (2007). Summarized, future research could use this dualistic approach in possible research designs: For example, the value and practice scores of The Globe Study could be used to compare to and explain existing findings delivered by negotiation research. Or, based on The Globe Study methodology to design own questionnaire items based on Values and Practices to address negotiation related research questions. Another possible approach may be based on The Globe Study's methodology to define own value-based questionnaire items that are tested and juxtaposed to behavioral data gathered from negotiation research experiments. Independently of the approach selected, if delivered congruent findings - i.e., similar value and practice data - it may further strengthen the arguments and conclusions derived from the findings. Second, in the case of non-congruent findings - i.e., significantly different data of values and practices – it may help to provide an explanation of why negotiators

behave differently and derive implications from these differences. Especially, these approaches are recommended for the reconciliation of the controversial findings that exist in the research field, as this review shows in Table 7.

5.2.3 Beyond Hofstede's IND dimension: The unaddressed potential of The Globe Study

Further, single findings referring to G-UAV and G-PDI were found in this review. Besides the G-I-COLL dimension, further dimensions of The Globe Study did not find application in negotiation research: G-FO, G-GE, and G-PO. In other words, for negotiation research, these additional dimensions are still terra incognita. Future research might address this gap. For example, there might be potential for future research using the G-FO dimension as a conceptual starting point, exploring how long-term-orientation in negotiations matches with results that deliver Hofstede's LTO dimension. An avenue for research could also represent the G-GE dimension, broadening existing research with the Cross-Cultural element of gender-related questions in Cross-Cultural-Negotiations. Last, G-PO could focus on individual rewards and how they affect motivation and negotiation outcomes. Summarized, Hofstede's five dimensions outweigh the dimensions of The Globe Study used by far with a share of 92,92% (Hofstede dimensions) compared to 7,08% (The Globe Study dimensions). Therefore, Hofstede's work can be considered as the standard model of reference in Cross-Cultural-Negotiation research, whereas The Globe Study is not established yet.

5.2.4 Use of The Globe Study: A recent trend?

However, it might be argued that Hofstede's work was the first large study that addressed cross-cultural differences in management, where a considerable share of Cross-Cultural-Negotiation literature had been published in continuation. In other words, The Globe Study might not exist long enough in order to find a larger application in Cross-Cultural-Negotiation research and hence only found consideration in the recent past. However, reviewing publication dates of the research findings in this review from the year 2000 – 2017, including clearly refutes this claim. This shows that Hofstede's work is – even though published almost 40 years ago – still dominating negotiation research- and that The Globe Study only found application sporadically in research in recent years and is far away from being equally considered (Appendix Fig. 3). Hence, research has missed widening the conceptual perspective so far by incorporating The Globe Study at a larger scale. Here, as Gunia and Gelfand (2016) highlighted, the need for further inclusion of The Globe Study into research exists. This overview could serve as an inventory and starting point for this endeavor by future research.

5.2.5 Information exchange and first offers in the Cross-Cultural-Context

Another conclusion of this review is the understanding of the field of research of information exchange and First Offers. Adair et al. (2007) showed that First Offers and information exchange are a connected phenomenon in low IND cultures: First offers are used as a medium of information exchange. Hence, neither first offers nor information exchange can be viewed separately in these cultures, rather than to be regarded as a combined phenomenon. Consequently, the attribution of information exchange to negotiation stage two and first offers to stage three of the four stages framework of Adair and Brett (2005) inhibits the investigation of this combined phenomenon for low IND cultures. The four stages framework should be updated with respect to this finding. It is recommended that future research uses for cultures along the IND continuum two approaches: For high IND cultures, first offers and information exchange can be investigated separately, but for low IND cultures, this subject needs to be regarded in combination in order to address its intertwined nature.

5.2.6 Unbalanced foci on research fields' sub-categories

With respect to the foci of research concerning Cross-Cultural-Negotiation sub-categories, it has been shown that research concentrates mostly on mainly one large research field, paying less attention to other topics. Negotiation strategies find by far the greatest resonance in research and, to a minor extent, the area of information exchange. These sub-categories show a relatively high diversity of cultural dimensions used. Several other directions of research, however, enjoy little attention, as for example, the use of rational influence, affective persuasion, and first offers. Especially the sub-category of first offers is considered to have a large impact on negotiation outcomes (e.g., Galinsky and Mussweiler 2001). Although there is research that embraces this topic in 'classical' negotiation research settings first offers in the cross-cultural-context lack larger consideration. Here future research should set a clear focus. This is especially important in order to meet the cultural complexity of this research discipline. With respect to the dimensional diversity, it is also shown that IND widely dominates the research sub-category landscape. This hampers conceptual advancement onto other areas that the multidisciplinary topic of Cross-Cultural-Negotiations offers. Hence, in these sub-categories also a diversity of dimensions is necessary in order to fully embrace their complexity. This opens up avenues for future research in two ways: First, to investigate these less addressed areas of research as, for example, the use of rational influence and affective persuasion. Future research could contribute further evidence in these fields delivering additional research results. Second, research could address these gaps by the use of conceptual constructs of culture that are underrepresented in the sub-category landscape, contributing evidence to these topics from a different conceptual perspective that may lead to an advancement in the research field.

5.2.7 Ambiguous findings using Hofstede's IND dimension

This review also displays that the critical disparity of the use of cultural dimensions shows some crucial disadvantages. Several topics had been subject to research that deliver contradicting results using Hofstede's IND dimension (Table 7). The use of competitive or cooperative negotiation strategies delivers contradicting results and is not yet fully understood: Low and high IND scores are ascribed to both cooperative and competitive negotiation strategies, resulting in the inability of Hofstede's IND dimension to sufficiently explain this phenomenon. It should also be mentioned that the use of The Globe Study's G-AS dimension delivered one ambiguous finding with respect to this topic. The following dimensions had been used providing more clarity: Cultures that score high in PDI and MAS, and low in G-HO are associated with the adoption of competitive negotiation strategies. Hence, these three dimensions are better suited as a predictor for the adoption of competitive vs. cooperative negotiation strategies than the IND dimension alone. Future research could also address further dimensional constructs, as, e.g., G-PO. House et al. (2004) attribute this dimension with the tendency of competitiveness vs. harmony. Hence, it is potentially suited to bring more clarity to this subject. As well as the G-AS dimension that harbors a similar potential due to its competition vs. cooperation attribution in Cross-Cultural-Research (House et al. 2004). Finally, Hofstede's UAV dimension may help to find additional support within this ambiguous finding with its 'competition is acceptable' vs. 'against competition' cultural attribution (Hofstede 2001). Another area of contradicting findings delivered by the use of IND is the investigation of possible cultural preferences using integrative information exchange in negotiations. With respect to this question, Hofstede's IND dimension also provides little guidance, as findings show that high and low IND scores are both ascribed to integrative information exchange. This review also shows that besides the IND dimension, there is no other dimension that has been used by research to explain this phenomenon. This opens up an avenue for future research, using other dimensions, as, e.g., Hofstede's PDI with its attributional effect of hierarchy on information: Constrained vs. Non constrained (Hofstede 2001). Also, The Globe Study's G-PDI dimension might provide a clearer assertion with the attribute of information localized vs. information shared (House et al. 2004). Another arena of ambiguous findings in the field of problem-solving approaches and their reciprocation is Hofstede's IND that delivers contradicting results in the findings. Cultures showing high and low IND scores are ascribed to both mentioned phenomena. Whereas with the PDI and LTO dimension, the topic of problem-solving approaches has been further investigated and shows unambiguous results. The research field of reciprocation of problem-solving approaches, however, indicates an avenue for future research, since there are not any further dimensions used by research to address this topic. Nevertheless, in both fields, the MAS dimension with its attribution of how conflicts

are solved: 'Problem-solving' vs. 'Conflict' (Hofstede 2001) might contribute valuable findings. The IND dimension is not alone subject to contradicting findings within the Hofstede framework. In addition, its PDI dimension as a conceptual approach to predict the adoption of power persuasion strategies shows contradicting results, too, associating its use to cultures with high and low PDI scores. Hence, Hofstede's PDI continuum cannot explain the use of power persuasion strategies in negotiations alone, rather than in combination with its IND dimension, showing that a culturally-rooted behavior in negotiation is more complex than being explicable in this case by one dimension alone. Future research might concentrate on the impact of the PDI and IND dimension in combination, rather than focusing on PDI only. Also, it might be promising for future research to expand the focus onto other unaddressed dimensions, as the G-HO dimension attributed by 'Power as a motivator' vs. 'Need for affiliation' (House et al. 2004), and G-AS: Value competition vs. Value cooperation (House et al. 2004). Both might help to bring more clarity to this subject. As shown in Table 7, there are five dimensions of Hofstede and one of The Globe Study that delivers contradicting results. What on one hand appears that Hofstede's dimensions deliver more contradicting results than The Globe Study may be explained by the limited use of The Globe Study dimensions in research. Here a future study could provide another snapshot in time about the development of cultural dimensions in this field and carve out whether the increased use of The Globe Study will deliver a higher share of contradicting results. Summarized, Hofstede's IND continuum should not be applied as a predictor for approaches in the following research fields: Competitive vs. Cooperative negotiation strategies, Integrative Information exchange, Problem-solving approach, and its reciprocation. However, IND can help in combination with PDI to explain the adoption of Power Persuasion Strategies better than using PDI alone. In addition, it might be helpful to exploit the full range of cultural dimensions of both, the remaining dimensions of Hofstede and especially the dimensions of The Globe Study shown, in order to further bring support to the mentioned phenomena.

Further, future research should especially control for the factors that influence the behavior of a negotiator besides national culture by, for example, including additional variables in research designs. For different contextual factors, exemplary publications can be found to lay to fundament for pathways to future research: To address the influence of regional cultures, the methodological design of House et al. (2004) could serve as a starting point. Concerning organizational culture, Kale (1996) may be helpful to develop the conceptual approach, and House et al. (2004) to derive an appropriate methodology. For external factors as the existing BATNA in negotiations, Buelens and Poulcke (2004) developed a methodology that could serve as a starting point for investigating the influence of the BATNA and the information available on different factors in the Cross-Cultural-Context. In the same context should be seen other than verbal communication and gender behavior, where Semnani-Azad and

Adair (2011, 2013) may offer a conceptual basis for further development. Additional factors as department culture, professional and educational culture, as well as family-based influences should be additionally controlled for in future research designs. Also, future research should control for the dynamics of culture in the Cross-Cultural-Negotiation context. This would enable a better comparison of results over time. Also, individual behavior in negotiations requires the attention of future research. Liu et al. (2012), for example, laid the fundament to address this issue by the five-factor model or Kale (1996) referring to the MBTI (Myers-Briggs-Type-Indicator). Both could serve as exemplary approaches to grasp the individual influence on cross-cultural-negotiations. Summarized, research should control more for the mentioned variables in future research designs accordingly and develop frameworks that take these into account.

Table 7 Contradicting findings in negotiation research

Research subject ^a	Dimensions showing contradicting results	Additional dimensions used in literature ^b	Conceptual basis for future research ^c	Bi-Polar dimensional attribution by cultural constructs of Hofstede and The Globe Study
Competitive vs. Cooperative Negotiation Strategy	IND	G-HO	G-PO	Competitiveness valued - Harmony valued (House, et al. 2004)
Integrative Information Exchange		MAS	G-AS	Value competition - Value cooperation (House, et al. 2004)
		PDI	UAV	Competition acceptable - Against competition (Hofstede 2001)
	IND	-	PDI	Hierarchy: Information constrained - Non constrained (Hofstede 2001)
Power Persuasion Strategy			G-PDI	Information is localized - Information is shared (House, et al. 2004)
	PDI	IND	G-HO	Motivator: Power - Need for belonging and affiliation (House, et al. 2004)
			G-AS	Value competition - Value cooperation (House, et al. 2004)
Problem Solving Approach	IND	PDI	MAS	Resolution of conflicts through problem solving - Resolution of problems through denying or fight (Hofstede 2001)
		LTO		
Reciprocation of Problem Solving Approach	IND	-	MAS	Resolution of conflicts through problem solving - Resolution of problems through denying or fight (Hofstede 2001)

^aResearch subjects that show contradicting findings in cross-cultural-negotiation research

^bAdditional dimensions in the literature that allow conclusions on the research subject

^cIdentified dimensions that show possible paths for future research

5.3 Concluding remarks

This review provides a state-of-the-art framework and a synthesis of Cross-Cultural-Negotiation research over more than 30 years. An approach for a review comprising relevant negotiation literature that uses Hofstede and The Globe Study as a cultural construct was imperative (Gunia and Gelfand 2016, Metcalf and Bird 2004, Graham 1994). This led to a holistic view of the research field that delivered several insights into the state of the art of research as well as point the way to future avenues of research. As it has been shown, Hofstede's Individuality dimension dominates the landscape of Cross-Cultural-Negotiation research. Considering the strong presence of the IND dimension as a benchmark, all other dimensions of Hofstede and The Globe Study lack consideration by research. This myopic view limits the development of the research field due to its one-sided focus on Hofstede's IND dimension. Research is seeing Cross-Cultural-Negotiations mainly through a one-dimensional lens of culture, i.e. the attributional characteristics on which the individualism-collectivism construct of Hofstede is based, limiting other perspectives that might produce a more diverse perception of the research field. As a consequence, other promising areas in the field of Cross-Cultural-Negotiation research might not be identified and followed. Another area that lacks diversity is the focus on negotiation strategies. It has been shown that this sub-category is prevailing in the literature, whereas other important fields of research lack consideration. This inhibits the development of other research areas that contribute to negotiation success, as, e.g., first offers. As for recommendations, future research should meet the complexity of Cross-Cultural-Negotiations by widening its view onto other cultural dimensions in order to form conceptual foundations based on the diversity of its dimensions. Hofstede and The Globe Study offer a variety of distinct dimensions that are well suited as a conceptual basis for future research. This would prepare the conceptual ground for meeting the interdisciplinary nature of Cross-Cultural-Negotiations and provide a more diverse insight into its sub-categories. Hence this review, due to its holistic approach, enables a starting point for future research. Further, as this review showed, the extensive use of Hofstede's IND delivered several ambiguous findings. In total, five research fields show contradicting findings using Hofstede dimensions, delivering no clear insight to which side of the bi-polar cultural dimensional constructs a research finding is pointing to. Four of the ambiguous findings are delivered by the use of Hofstede's IND dimension, one by its PDI dimension. It has been shown that other cultural dimensions of Hofstede and The Globe Study would also be appropriate to explore the mentioned topics since they bear the potential to shed further light on these controversial findings. Since the research gaps and their potential dimensional approaches are displayed in Table 7, this review serves as a comprehensive overview designing future research. In this phase,

future research needs to address the question on which cultural construct the work will be based on. For the use of either framework – Hofstede or The Globe Study – there are good reasons: Arguments for the ongoing use of Hofstede and especially its IND dimension is the strong sample size and that it allows comparability of the studies already conducted in this field. Arguments for a more prevalent use of The Globe Study are: First, possible changes in culture since Hofstede’s publications could be better addressed since its results display a more recent snapshot in time. Second, the potential distortion of company and industry culture influences had been widely excluded. Third, the presence of data of sub-cultures, and, fourth, the higher amount of available dimensions providing new perspectives onto the research field. Summarized, there might be more reasons that speak for the use of The Globe Study. However, finally, this decision depends on various factors, including the research subject, the research question, and its objectives. This review represents a starting point for future research giving a state-of-the-art overview of the research field that eases researchers making a balanced decision to opt for one of both cultural constructs.

Appendix

Table 8 Abbreviations for the identified dimensions

Hofstede Framework		The Globe Study Framework	
Abbreviation	Dimension	Abbreviation	Dimension
IND	Individuality Index	G-AS	Assertiveness Score
PDI	Power Distance Index	G-FO	Future Orientation Score
MAS	Masculinity Index	G-GE	Gender Egalitarianism Score
UAV	Uncertainty Avoidance Index	G-HO	Humane Orientation Score
LTO	Long-Term Orientation Index ^a	G-G-COLL	In-Group Collectivism Score
		G-I-GOLL	Institutional Collectivism Score
		G-PO	Performance Orientation Score
		G-PDI	Power Distance Score
		G-UAV	Uncertainty Avoidance Score

^aDeveloped by Hofstede and Bond (1988)

Fig. 3 Temporal overview of publications using Hofstede or Globe as a conceptual basis from 2000 – 2017

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